

Analysing the above powder file, the system was found to be orthorhombic with $a=24.82 \pm 0.02$, $b=10.20 \pm 0.02$, $c=11.10 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha+\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$. So the volume V per unit cell was calculated to be $2.805.68 \text{ \AA}^3$. The space group was uniquely established to be I_4 / a and number of molecules per unit

cell Z was found to be 2. The measured density $\rho_{\text{obs.}}=2.46 \text{ gml}^{-1}$. From the relation $\rho_{\text{obs.}} = \frac{1.66M.Z}{V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the com-

pound to be 2080 against the theoretical value 2109.8.

Discussion

Application of pH and thermometric studies remove much of the uncertainty about the real amount of reactants to be taken for the preparation of heteropoly compounds. It has been observed that the continuation of addition of the reactants did not indicate any possibility of appearance of higher homologue of the series. The generally accepted principle that the condensation of heteropoly acids and their compounds depend on hydrogen ion concentrations has been further corroborated as the complex anion of the tungstoantimonate appeared within pH 5.50. The structure of the compound can be compared with the structure of complex heteroan-

nion $[X_n W_6 O_{24}]^{12-n-}$ suggested by Keggin⁷, and Illingworth¹². Six WO_6 octahedra are to be arranged in a hexagonal annulus so as to share two corners with each of the two neighbouring octahedra. The central cavity of resulting $[W_6 O_{24}]^{12-}$ will just accommodate one octahedron of SbO_6 . The capacity of Sb to behave with 6-coordination number may have a confirmation from the radius ratio rule, $r_{sb} : r_{O^{2-}}$ as 0.44, predicting a coordination number 6. so for Sb. Large number of water molecules find position in the empty space of the crystal to give a resultant hydrated structure.

Acknowledgement

We express our thanks to the authorities of Planning and Development Division, Sindri, for their active cooperation in the X-ray work.

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Chalcones. XXIII. Germicides Derived from Acetyl Phenanthrenes and Naphthalene

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Manuscript received 14 January 1977, accepted 31 March 1977

CONTINUING our study of potential germicides¹⁻⁷ of biochemical importance, we undertook the preparation, characterization and biochemical screening, against gram (+ve) and (-ve) bacteria, of phenanthryl and naphthyl chalcones. These compounds are of interest not only because they contain an α, β -unsaturated carbonyl linkage as a bridge between a phenanthryl moiety and phenyl nucleus, but also because of the reported multiprotecting biochemical activities viz. antibacterial⁸, antifungal⁹, sedative¹⁰, germicidal¹¹, antifertility¹², etc.

The synthesis of these compounds started by condensation of 2- and 3-acetyl phenanthrenes, 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone with substituted benzaldehydes according to the specified procedure³ (Table 1).

The structure of compounds under study follow from the method of synthesis and are confirmed by their elemental analyses, halochromic effect with Conc. H_2SO_4 , 2:4-DNP preparation and by recording absorption spectra of compounds 1, 3, 10 and 13 in the infrared region. The infrared spectra of compounds contain characteristic frequencies corresponding to the individual peculiar features of their structures, and are investigated mainly for their carbonyl frequency. Thus, the absorption bands in the region 1667-1681 cm^{-1} were characteristic¹³ of α, β -unsaturated ketonic group. The effect of neighbouring groups and bi- and tricyclic rings in the frequency has been discussed in an earlier communication¹². All compounds analysed satisfactorily for C, H and N.

Experimental

2- and 3-acetyl phenanthrenes and 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone were prepared according to the standard procedure.

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TABLE-1 : PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHALCONE ANALOGUES
Ar'-CO-CH=CH-Ar

Ar'	Ar	Colour & crystal form	M.P.°C	Yield %	Time of reaction(hr.)	Halochromism conc.CH ₂ SO ₄	Diameter of zone of inhib. in mm.
1. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	2-OH-3-OCH ₃ Ph	ON	123	41	48	brown	—
2. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	3-OH-4-OCH ₃ Ph	LYN	109 (193)*	38	48	ruby-red	—
3. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	4-OCH ₃ Ph	RPr	158	53	36	purple	—
4. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	2-OAc	LYP	117	40	50	cherry-red	—
5. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	3-OAc ^f	LYG	121	35	50	dark orange	—
6. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	2-Cl	ON	139 (217)*	83	24	brown red	11
7. 2'-OH-1'-naphthyl	3-Cl	ORP	133	78	24	lemon yellow	10
8. 2'-Phenanthryl	2 OAc ^f	LYG	93d	40	50	orange	7
9. 2'-Phenanthryl	3 OC ₂ H ₅	YG	103	43	50	dirty yellow	—
10. 2'-Phenanthryl	2 : 3-(OCH ₃) ₂	YN	126 (207)*	60	36	yellow	—
11. 3'-Phenanthryl	2-Cl ^f	YN	122	83	24	cherry-red	11
12. 3'-Phenanthryl	3-NO ₂	YPr	178	65	20	red	10
13. 3'-Phenanthryl	4-OAc	YG	112d	56	48	brown	—

O = orange : Y = yellow : L = lemon : P = plate : Pr = prism : R = red : G = globules

N = needles *m.p. of 2,4-DNP

f = crystallised from benzene

The synthesis of chalcones achieved by Claisen-Schmidt condensation of appropriate methyl aryl ketones (0.005 mol.) and benzaldehydes (0.005 mol.) using saturated solution of sodium in methanol as condensing agent. One typical example is cited below.

An equimolar ethanolic solution of 3-acetyl phenanthrene and 2-chloro benzaldehyde was treated with Na/MeOH solution at 20-25° with constant stirring on a magnetic stirrer. The dark coloured reaction mixture (after 2 hr.) was kept at room temperature for 24 hr. The deposited compound was collected and the filtrate upon ice/HCl treatment gave a crude product which was crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Pharmacology :

The germicidal property was assayed by following agar-cup method using peptone, beef extract agar-agar as solid nutrient broth media. The bacteria selected for the screening were *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The inhibition of growth was checked in a presterilized petridish after 24 hr. and results are recorded by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to authorities of H.B.T.I., Kanpur for providing necessary facilities, the Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for getting analyses and ir spectra. I also acknowledge the assistance of Mrs. Bimla Misra and Mr. Gokaran Nath Misra during the work and constant encouragement of Dr. Durga Nath Dhar, I.I.T., Kanpur.

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2-Hydroxy-1, 4-naphthalenedione (Lawson) A pH Indicator

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Manuscript received 13 February 1976, revised 5 August 1976, accepted 10 February, 1977

THE role of lawson as a chelating agent is well documented¹⁻⁷. Recently Sawhney and Trehan introduced juglone as a pH indicator⁸. However no mention has been made in literature regarding how the title compound behaves structurally under the influence of hydrogen ion concentration.

Experimental

All the reagents employed were of analytical grade. Baush and Lomb Spectronic 20, Spectrophotometer was used for absorption studies. Different sets containing varying hydrogen ion concentrations